

A Study of Traditional Agricultural Practices in Khasi Society in Janice Pariat's *Everything the Light Touches*

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This paper aims to focus on the traditional practices in farming and the way human-nature bond has developed through the journey of cultivation in human civilization. The main geographical region to be discussed in this paper would be that of Meghalaya as it forms a central part of the novel to be discussed here. *Everything the Light Touches* is Janice Pariat's latest work in fiction. It involves four stories- about four characters that are spread across space and time. Here, much importance will be given to two characters and their narratives namely, those of Shai and Evelyn.

The novel attempts at looking into the anthropocentric limits that the contemporary human beings face as a result of being distanced from nature. This binary between the modern and the traditional approach towards nature is evident in the story of Shai. Moreover, the contemporary problem of uranium mining in Meghalaya has also been addressed. The theory of Environmental Humanities will be applied while reading this text. This theory delves into the study of nature or the environment as a living entity that cannot be undervalued as merely the background.

Keywords : Anthropocentrism, Environmental Humanism, Nature, Traditional cultivation.